

region 1020-1070 cm^{-1} , $\Delta\nu$ for the complex were 0 to +9 cm^{-1} and confirmed the C=S assignment of the bands. As the C-O-C frequencies of the complex are expected to be higher than the alkali xanthate, the absorption frequencies of the complex at 1275 and 1260 cm^{-1} may be attributed to C-O-C linkage.

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Chemical Constituents of the Flowers of *Strobilanthes callosus* (Acanthaceae)

M. ILYAS*, (MISS) RANJANA VERMA and (MISS)
PARVEEN JAMAL

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh—202001

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STROBILANTHES callosus Nees, is a herb having yellowish flowers with spikes and panicles. In India plant is commonly known as Karvi. Flowers and leaves are used for different purposes¹⁻². No chemical studies have so far been reported on this plant.

Air dried flowers were extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The concentrated extract was divided into acidic and neutral fraction by usual method. The neutral fraction on column chromatography over neutral alumina gave four different substances marked A, B, C, and D.

The GLC analysis of the substance A m.p. 62-67° over 3% SE 30 column at 250° showed it to be a mixture of n-alkanes containing hentriacontane (36.3%), tritriacontane (28.9%), nonacosane (21.2%), dotriacontane (4.5%) and triacontane (2.9%), heptacosane (2.0%), hexatriacontane (1.5%), tetratriacontane (1.0%), octacosane (1.0%) accompanied by hexacosane, pentacosane, and pentatriacontane as a minor constituent. Fraction B m.p. 79-80° was classified as saturated alcohol by I.R.

and Co-TLC. GLC analysis showed it to be a mixture of n-alcohols containing tetratriacontanol (40.5%), dotriacontanol (30.5%), tritriacontanol (20.8%), triacontanol (4.3%), hentriacontanol (3.6%). Nonacosanol, pentatriacontanol, and hexatriacontanol was also found as a trace constituent.

The compound C m.p. 210° gave positive Liebermann Burchard and Noller's test. I.R., m.p., m.m.p. and Co-TLC showed it to be lupeol. Compound D m.p. was identified as sterol by Liebermann Burchard and Noller's test. GC-MS analysis³ showed it to be a mixture of four sterols. Cholesterol (0.4%) (M^+ 458), campesterol (11.0%) (M^+ 472), stigmasterol (41.5%) (M^+ 484) and β -sitosterol (47.0%) (M^+ 486).

The acidic fraction contains mainly saturated fatty acids m.p. 65°. GLC analysis at 250° showed it to be a mixture of C_{24} - C_{30} fatty acids; pentacosanoic acid (54.0%), heptacosanoic acid (22.5%), nonacosanoic acid (8.5%), hexacosanoic acid (6.2%), octacosanoic acid (3.5%), pentatriacontanoic acid (2.6%) and hentriacontanoic acid (2.3%) along with the minor quantities of triacontanoic acid and heptatriacontanoic acid.

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Base Adducts of Bis (Acetylacetonato) Zinc(II) with Nitrogen Donors

C. D. RAO, D. SATYANARAYANA and B. K. MOHAPATRA
Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack 753 008

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LEWIS acid behaviour of metal chelates of β -diketones and related compounds which involve keto-enol tautomerism have invoked lot of interest in recent years. Stability of β -diketonates has been partly explained on the basis of benzenoid resonance¹ and reactions characteristic of aromatic system have been carried out²⁻⁴ on metal β -diketonates to provide further evidence regarding the aromaticity. We have been trying for the adduct formation of metal β -diketonates with heterocyclic bases and isolated a number adducts of Zinc(II)⁵⁻⁷ and Copper(II)^{8,9} β -diketonates with